

Real and Virtual Wireless Radio Network Emulator

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Abstract—In this paper, we discuss the use of the RF Wireless Network Environment emulator. Its architecture and capabilities are investigated. Four case studies of the RF network emulator are presented in this paper. The first case study simulates the slow-hopping anti-jamming waveform. The second case study is the application of spectrum masking, the third is the use of power difference of arrival localization algorithm to triangulate the location of a local unknown emitter and the fourth utilizes the emulator for testing and verification of a Multiple Link Common Data Link System. The network architecture and setup of the environment emulator for each case is discussed in detail.

I. INTRODUCTION

When testing and implementing RF communications and wireless networks, it is often useful to have the ability to observe particular environmental effects on a network in a controlled environment in order to identify particular channel properties that affect the communications network. The RFnest™, developed by Intelligent Automation Inc. (IAI) consists of an RF environment emulator that is useful for replicating channel effects similar to those that are observed in the implementation of a full-scale field test. There are significant advantages to having the ability to conduct field tests in a testbed that emulates the physical properties of the environment, including: repeatability, realism, and cost. Implementing real field tests is significantly more expensive and it is difficult to replicate and repeat similar channel conditions and scenarios in a physical environment.

The RF Wireless Network Environment Emulator (RWFNEE) has the capability to emulate real life wireless channels to evaluate wireless radio networks in a laboratory environment with high fidelity. The RWFNEE can produce and host a wireless network environment with wireless channel properties, such as range attenuation, range delay, multipath, Doppler effect and interferences. The RWFNEE also provides a capability for examining network scaling effects by allowing communications between real and virtual radios. Virtual radio nodes are emulated by the Naval Research Laboratory's (NRL) Extendable Mobile Ad-hoc Network Emulator (EMANE) [1] [2]. Communications between real and virtual radios are accomplished through a Surrogate Virtual Receiver/Surrogate Virtual Transmitter (SVR/SVT) [1].

In this paper, we discuss the architecture of the RWFNEE and four case studies examined are implemented with the details, simulation setup and results for each. Brief descriptions of the case studies are listed as follows:

- slow-hopping anti-jam waveform (SHAW): an interference source is added and the SHAW waveform is simulated over a channel for both static and dynamic scenarios
- spectrum masking: the doppler shift and delay function of the RFnest is utilized in order to emulate the latency of the signal
- emitter localization: a local unknown emitter's position is triangulated by a mesh sensor network using power difference of arrival (PDOA)
- Multiple Link CDL System Testing: software and hardware development testing is recursive, and use of the RWFNEE is used to test a Multiple Link Common Data Link System (MLCS) to configure and operate various software and hardware interfaces

II. RF WIRELESS NETWORK ENVIRONMENT EMULATOR ARCHITECTURE

Currently the RWFNEE has an operating band of [20 MHz - 6 GHz] with linearity optimized for the [20 MHz - 3 GHz] band, a dynamic range of 60 dB per channel, a maximum propagation delay of 2 sec, a maximum multipath tap per channel of 20, a Doppler shift of 200 kHz per path and various fading profiles such as frequency selective, frequency flat fading, Rayleigh, Rician, pure Doppler, frequency shift, phase shift and log-normal. The emulator supports a variety of network configurations such as SISO, MIMO, MISO, SIMO, and fully meshed.

The main component of the RWFNEE is IAI's RFnest™ D512 RF channel emulator. With the D512 emulator, the current set up can support a meshed network of twelve nodes and the network size is expandable. As it is depicted in Fig. (1), the radio under test (RUT) is interfaced with the D512 through the RF daughter board (RFDB), which is responsible for conversion between RF and IF bands for transmitted and received signals. The digital daughter board (DDB) interfaces with the RFDB and the main FPGA board and it has high speed ADCs and DACs for conversion between analog and digital domain. In addition, each DDB has a mid-size FPGA, which is used for signal multiplexing in order to maximize the transmission capacity between the DDB and the main FPGA. The main FPGA is the RF channel emulation engine and it is capable of supporting up to a 48 node full meshed network in half-duplex mode. The expansion board allows the D512 chassis to be expanded and multiple chassis can be joined

Fig. 1. RFNest Architecture

through a Gigabit Ethernet to support evaluation of a large scale wireless network. [3].

The RFNestTM D512 is controlled through a software module which controls scenario generation, channel modeling, and virtual/real node operation among tactical radios. To protect signal integrity each RUT is enclosed in an RF shielded enclosure to prevent over-the-air leakage of RF signals. For testing scenarios involving geolocation, a GPS simulator is provided for each RUT. USB base real-time spectrum analyzers (RSA) are also provided for spectrum monitoring and management purposes. A network of computers is integrated to execute emulations for scenarios but this is not currently implemented.

As depicted in Fig. (1), these computers contain control software for the emulation system as well as providing an interface for EMANE functionality and manipulation. These machines are then connected into the local network, via switches and patch panels, which creates the backbone of the RFWNEE. Currently this local network connects nine endpoint nodes that can be accessed to run simulations remotely; additional nodes may be added as needed. A picture of the entire physical setup RFNest and its key components, is shown in Fig. (16).

III. CASE STUDY: SHAW WAVEFORM

This section describes simulation and testing of the RFNest-WE with a pair of frequency-hopping radios. In particular, we tested with a slow-hopping anti-jam waveform (SHAW).

This frequency-hopping system consists of 8 channels, starting at 1002 MHz with 100 MHz spacing between each channel. SHAW uses GMSK modulation, with dwell times at 100 milliseconds. Although the hop rate is slow for modern systems, the wide frequency range makes it difficult to detect the complete hopping pattern. SHAW typically covers a much wider range, usually 2 to 3 GHz. Due to hardware limitations in RFNestTM, the full 3 GHz band could not be simulated, so the frequency range was reduced to 700 MHz by eliminating higher frequency channels.

Our previous work with the SHAW waveform, and which is what the following RFNest doppler shift experiment is based off of, can be found in [6]. The SHAW waveform was generated using a USRP, a commercially available software-defined radio. Two nodes were created, one for the transmitter, and another for the receiver. A third node was used as an interference source. These nodes were connected to RFNest for channel simulation. Fig. (2) shows the hardware setup. The USRPs are configured half-duplex, with one RF connection for both transmission and reception. The power splitter separates multiple bands for each node. The RFNestTM has a maximum bandwidth limitation of 250 MHz from the center frequency, which follows from its maximum sampling rate of 4 nsec. Due to filter roll-off, the actual frequency response is closer to +/- 200 MHz.

Because the SHAW frequency range is greater than the

Fig. 2. Block Diagram of SHAW Waveform Emulation with RFNest™

Fig. 3. Shaw error rate

maximum bandwidth, multiple ports were used to construct the bandwidth necessary for the channel emulation of the entire waveform. Given a hopset with center frequencies from 1002 to 1702 MHz, four ports were needed to cover the 700 MHz range. Each radio node therefore required 4 ports, and the testing of two nodes required 8 ports. A ninth port was used as an interface for the interference source.

Using the network emulator, the SHAW radios were tested and measured under a variety of scenarios. First, the receiver sensitivity was measured. Next, SHAW was tested under varying Doppler shifts, and its packet loss ratio was measured. SHAW performance was measured in the presence of an interfering source, with one of its channels blocked. SHAW performance was tested under varying signal-to-noise ratios. Finally, a mobile scenario was tested, with the SHAW radios undergoing dynamic path loss, Doppler shift, and delay.

Sensitivity testing was performed on the SHAW radios. The transmitter output power was placed at 0 dBm. We measured the dynamic range of the receiver. At default gain values, the receiver demodulated signals accurately from -92 dBm to -18 dBm. Below -92 dBm, the receiver's packet error rate is significantly degraded. At -107 dBm, no packets were detected, and this level is considered the receiver's minimum sensitivity.

The emulator simulated various Doppler shifts, and the results are shown in Fig. (3). During testing, UDP packets were sent from the SHAW Transmitter to the SHAW receiver.

Fig. 4. Noise Testing

Fig. 5. Flight Path

The received packets were recorded, and packet losses were determined by investigating the sequence number. The packet loss ratio was calculated by dividing the lost packets by the total packets sent. The tests were first conducted without interference. To further stress the SHAW radios, these tests were also performed with an interfering source. During interference testing, the signal generator was used at a fixed frequency, blocking one of the eight SHAW channels. As seen in the figure, the SHAW communication system worked well for Doppler shifts less than 20 kHz, positive or negative.

The SHAW waveform was also tested under varying signal-to-noise ratios. The noise source was injected through the RF Nest, and the noise gain was adjusted to vary the SNR. The results of the packet loss ratio for this is shown in Fig. (4) .

Finally a mobile scenario was run, simulating ground-to-air communications. The route is shown in Fig. (5). The transmitter's location remained fixed, while the receiver moved around a square perimeter. The emulator simulated the path loss, Doppler shift, and delay caused by the receiver's movement. Simulations were run under three different transmitter powers at 5, 10, and 15 dBm. Fig. (6) shows the results of these simulations. In this mobile scenario, As transmitter power increased, the packet loss ratio decreased as expected.

Fig. 6. Flight Path

IV. CASE STUDY: SPECTRUM MASKING

Spectrum masking is used to identify the spectrum of a predicted signal. If the signal is fixed, the mask then reports a correct signal; otherwise reports are generated for the signal as above or below the mask. The reports are generated for no match if the signal's bandwidth is outside the bandwidth's range, or the signal's amplitude is too low. If the signal in the operating bandwidth was detected with a broadband noise; it is reported as jamming. The classification of the jamming characteristic depends on whether the amplitude is above, below, or in between the spectrum mask. The algorithm for the spectrum masking requires the RF emulator Fig. (7) to generate various input signals or apply an input from USRP's output, so the RF sensor can classify and then report the results as seen in Figs. (8) and (9). The RF emulator can generate channel noise and control latency, multi-path, and Doppler

Fig. 7. Block diagram for spectrum masking

Fig. 8. Correct Signal

Fig. 9. No match

effects. With spectrum mask detection, the Doppler effect function of the RF emulator is important since the masking algorithm must account for the frequency shift associated with the Doppler, and the RF emulator provides the signal associated with the relative motion of the signal source. Fig. (10) demonstrates the characteristics of the signal source moving away from the sensor.

For the development and testing of the spectrum mask program, we need different input signals and spectrum environments for the sensor. To create these simulated signals for the input to spectrum mask sensor, we used Matlab™ and RF emulator record/playback functions. The input signals are generated with Matlab™ played back using the functionality in the RF emulator. The playback function operates at base-band, however USRPs are most often used to provide signal flexibility and allow operation at a variety of RF bands. These signals can be used as input (TX signal) for the emulator. Another USRP (RF sensor) at the other end of the output channel (RX signal) runs the spectrum masking algorithm. Matlab™ can also be used to generate a signal noise file, where the same record and playback technique can be used to read the noise from the Matlab™ file and inject the environment noise into the channel using the playback function in the GUI.

V. CASE STUDY: PDOA EMITTER LOCALIZATION

This section describes the simulation and testing of the Power difference of arrival localization of a single emitter on the RFnest™ wireless network emulator. This network setup uses four USRPs in a mesh network configuration. Three of the USRPs will sense the power level at the frequency in which the emitter is tuned to and will send a packet with

Fig. 10. Doppler effect on frequency

Fig. 12. PDOA scenario map

Fig. 11. PDOA scenario hardware setup

Fig. 13. PDOA error in location estimation

the payload consisting of the power report and the location of the transmitting sensor. The packets containing information necessary to triangulate the location of the local emitter are sent to a fourth USRP in the network, referred to as the fusion node. The fusion node performs the triangulation using the power reports and location of each sensor to triangulate the location by taking the power difference between each pair of sensors, and using the log-distance path loss model with $\alpha = 2.4$, to generate circles where the intersection between each pair of circles is found. Grid-density based search for the grid cell with the most intersections is utilized and details are discussed in [4]. The location of the sensors was generated using a GPS simulator. The network is shown in Fig. (11) with the same setup consisting of a USRP attached to the host PC and GPS simulator for ports 1 through 4 of the RFnest™ hardware.

The map of the scenario shown in Fig. (12) illustrates the layout and simulated location of the USRPs in the network. In the lab setup, a signal generator transmits a sinusoidal waveform at 903 MHz and -20 dBm, which is the optimal level to achieve the dynamic range for the channel between the links. The USRPs are communicating with each other over 920 MHz where the emulator hardware has its center frequency set

to 850 MHz. These frequencies will still be detected by the emulator because of the 250 MHz bandwidth of the RFnest™ hardware. The USRPs were set with a gain of 10 dBm so that the power at the input port was -20 dBm. The transmit power offset is also adjusted to compensate for the insertion loss and cable loss so that the receiver could demodulate the signal packet within the -35 dBm to -75 dBm range. The TPO also had to be adjusted to compensate for the fact that the emitter in the field test would transmit at 12 dBm since the maximum tolerance for input to the ports is -10 dBm.

For one iteration of the PDOA simulation, the fusion node will send a request to receive the packets of the sensors. There is a five second time interval between the packet request and transmit period so each iteration lasts approximately 5 seconds where all sensors send their packets and the fusion node triangulates the position of the emitter.

Fig. (13) shows the results of 100 iterations of the PDOA triangulation where the error in location estimation was calculated by finding the distance between the actual location of the emitter and the estimated location by the algorithm. The results from the previous field test, which are shown in [5] showed

Fig. 14. MLCS hardware setup

Fig. 15. MLCS Graphical User Interface

an average RMSE (in meters) of the emitter localization of approximately (20 meters, for three sensors and an emitter inside the network). The difference in average error between actual field test results and RFNWEE simulation results arises due to the unpredictable path loss and environmental variables of the actual field test results, and the smaller variance in the RFNWEE simulation results arises from the repeatability of working in a controlled laboratory environment.

VI. CASE STUDY: MULTIPLE LINK CDL SYSTEM TESTING

Software development is a recursive process that involves verification through testing and in some cases simulation tools may not be enough to achieve a desired level of confidence due to limited operational and environmental constraints. This section describes how the RFWNEE is used for testing and verification of the Multiple Link Common Data Link System (MLCS). MLCS provides the processes to configure, operate and coordinate other hardware and software interfaces as required to conduct up to four simultaneous Common Data Link (CDL) missions. MLCS is funded by the Office of Naval Research and developed by the Naval Surface Warfare Center Dahlgreen Division (NSWCDD) and the U.S. Naval Research Laboratory.

Our testing scenario consists of establishing a line of sight (LOS) communications CDL link between a surface and air platform using two Multiband Mini Transceivers (MMT) CDL modems. MLCS is capable of searching and tracking a remote platform based on Receive Signal Strength (RSS) and/or Standard Navigational Information (NAV).

These two modems connect to the RFnest™ for channel simulation as shown in Fig. (14). Because these modems are full duplex, each of them use two of the RFnest™ ports as shown in Fig. (14). Due to the RFnest™ operating frequencies limitation, we operate the modems in L-band frequencies. Two GPS simulators are used to provide position information to each platform. The GPS receivers are used to lock on to the GPS signal generated by the GPS simulators and provide

GPS coordinates to each modem as well as send position updates messages to the RFnest™'s Channel Emulation Controller (CEC) for channel characteristics updates. We start a link or mission by tracking our airborne platform modem using its position information known to the system. Once a link is established, the RFnest™ will continue updating the channel characteristics as it receives new position updates from the platform. Being able to simulate the RF channel and vehicular motion enables tracking experiments that would otherwise involve expensive testing assets. Software testing under simulated conditions enables verification of the software performance at different repetitive scenarios under a variety of vehicular dynamics and propagation characteristics.

VII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Use of the RFNWEE wireless network environment emulator has proven useful for demonstrating the capabilities for future work in simulating research scenarios, such as frequency hopping, emitter localization, and spectrum masking. Future use of the RFWNEE would allow for more controllable testing of radio communications and to more easily observe channel effects on the radios such as channel attenuation models, doppler shift, and delay. RFWNEE results would serve as a valuable tool for establishing correspondence between actual field test results and theoretical results.

Fig. 16. RFNWEE physical laboratory setup

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